

is found to be the same order, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} \sim \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ as for the corresponding binary ML complexes.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES IN 50% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER MEDIUM

$I=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$

Cation	$\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$	$\log K_{\text{ML}_2}^{\text{ML}}$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$		$\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$
	30°	30°	30°	40°	
H ⁺	9.13	6.58	—	—	—
Cu ^{II}	6.65	4.60	3.20	3.17	-3.45
Ni ^{II}	4.70	3.98	2.58	2.47	-2.17
Co ^{II}	4.53	3.48	2.73	2.73	-1.75

The $\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$ values^a (Table 1) for all M(NTA)-(L) complexes are negative. Higher negative value of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ as compared to $\Delta \log K_{\text{Ni}}$ probably arises out of Jahn-Teller distortion in the case of Cu^{II} complexes.

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Phenyl Acetate Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Manuscript received 28 January 1987, revised 24 September 1987, accepted 30 October 1987

In this communication, we report the studies on Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} , phenyl acetates with quinoline, isoquinoline and 3-methylpyridine.

Experimental

Metal carbonates were reacted in stoichiometric proportion with alcoholic solution of phenylacetic acid on a water-bath. Alcoholic solution of metal phenyl acetates were treated with nitrogen ligands in 1:2 proportion and the solution refluxed for 0.5 h over a water-bath. Volume of the solution

was reduced to 5 ml by rotary vacuum evaporator and kept overnight when crystalline compounds separated out. The compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum. All complexes were found to be crystalline—Ni and Cu complexes green, Co complexes pink and Zn complexes white. Metal and nitrogen in the complexes were estimated by standard methods; conductance in acetone, magnetic moment at room temperature (Table 1), ir spectra (KBr) and electronic spectra (chloroform) were recorded.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF PHENYL ACETATE COMPLEXES

Compd ^a	Conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)	
			Metal	N
NiL_2Q_2	8.5	2.9	9.95 (10.07)	4.45 (4.77)
$\text{NiL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	9.2	2.98	9.83 (10.07)	4.52 (4.77)
$\text{NiL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	8.1	3.15	11.14 (11.40)	5.28 (5.44)
CoL_2Q_2	9.5	4.84	9.86 (10.03)	4.53 (4.77)
$\text{CoL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	8.8	4.96	9.91 (10.03)	4.55 (4.77)
$\text{CoL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	10.2	5.1	11.22 (11.46)	5.26 (5.44)
CuL_2Q_2	11.5	1.75	10.56 (10.74)	4.48 (4.73)
$\text{CuL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	11.8	1.83	11.62 (10.74)	4.48 (4.73)
$\text{CuL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	12.6	1.88	12.01 (12.28)	5.26 (5.39)
ZnL_2Q_2	10.5	—	10.92 (11.02)	4.51 (4.72)
$\text{ZnL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	13.8	—	10.86 (11.02)	4.60 (4.72)
$\text{ZnL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	14.7	—	12.25 (12.54)	5.22 (5.37)

^aQ=Quinoline, I.Q=Isoquinoline, β -pio=3-methylpyridine.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are crystalline and have the composition ML_2B_2 , where L is the phenyl acetate and B is the nitrogen base. These are fairly low melting solids and soluble in common organic solvents. Lower values of molar conductance suggest their non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment values of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes at room temperature (25°) are indicative of high-spin octahedral configuration. Cu^{II} complexes have magnetic moment in the normal range.

In sodium phenyl acetate asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching frequencies appear at 1610 and 1400 cm^{-1} , respectively¹. These bands are shifted to slightly lower frequency regions in the transition metal phenyl acetates and shift to higher frequency regions (around 1420 and 1630 cm^{-1}) respectively, in the complexes with nitrogen ligands. Further, most of the bands due to free nitrogen ligands are shifted to lower frequency region in most of the complexes indicating their coordination to the metal ions. This has been further supported

by the observation² of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} around 450 and 350 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the far-infrared region. The difference between the asymmetric and symmetric C-O stretching modes is of the order of 210–220 cm^{-1} , indicating bidentate nature of the acetate² groups as this difference will be of higher order for monodentate acetate groups.

In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes in chloroform solution three absorption bands appear in the 9.0, 15.0 and 25.0 kK regions assignable⁴ to $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{2g}(F)$, $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$, $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, indicating octahedral configuration. Extinction coefficient values (6, 13 and 20, respectively) also support this configuration. Comparison of the bands of a similar compound with the diffuse reflectance spectra reported⁵ indicates a little dissociation of the ligand in spite of the added base, as the bands in solution spectra are at lower energy. It is quite probable that there is a distortion of the octahedron in solution as the two nitrogen ligands are in the trans position.

Cobalt(II) complexes give rise to two absorption bands around 8.0 and 19.5 kK regions, which can be assigned⁶ to $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{2g}(F)$ and $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. These absorption bands and extinction coefficient values (9.5 and 13, respectively) also show an octahedral geometry for these complexes.

Copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band at 15.5 kK region suggesting a distorted octahedral structure for the copper(II) complexes⁷. Zinc complexes presumably have an octahedral environment around the metal ion involving bidentate acetate group.

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Studies of some Metal Chelates of Ketoanils Part-II

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Manuscript received 18 November 1986, revised 8 October 1987,
accepted 30 October 1987

ALTHOUGH, *para*-substituted ketoanils which coordinate usually through their carbonyl and azomethine groups in quinonoid structure and

generally form polymeric and isomeric complexes of unusual stoichiometries have been synthesised and characterised¹⁻³ for past two decades, *ortho*-substituted ketoanils, however, have not been exploited for their ligation properties as yet. It was, therefore, considered of interest to synthesise thio-phenene-2-glyoxal-*o*-pyridineanil (TGPA) and to study its coordination properties in conjugation with a few 3d-metal ions. Present paper reports the synthesis, structure and properties of TGPA and its complexes with iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II).

Experimental

Isolation of TGPA and its complexes: TGPA was obtained⁴ as brown precipitate on mixing solutions containing equimolar quantities of thio-phenene-2-glyoxal and *o*-aminopyridine in ether. The product was purified by reprecipitation from acetone with ether and was dried in oven at $\sim 40^\circ$. It was found to be soluble in chloroform, acetone and alcohol.

For the preparation of complexes, saturated solution in acetone of the ligand was added slowly to a saturated solution in acetone of metal chlorides with constant stirring; reaction mixtures containing stoichiometric amounts of reactants were evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and residues were washed with chloroform and then with water to remove unreacted ligand and metal chloride, respectively. This procedure was not followed in the preparation of complexes from cupric chloride and ferric sulphate as they were precipitated in good yield while mixing the reactants in acetone and alcohol, respectively.

Resolution of binary mixtures: Thin layer chromatography on starch-bound silica gel layers indicated that cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes were binary mixtures. The mixtures were quantitatively resolved by column chromatography which was conducted in columns (50 cm \times 2 cm dia) containing silica gel (50–100 mesh, B.D.H.). The column was loaded with sample solution in dioxan and was developed with acetone-chloroform (9 : 1, v/v) solvent. Slow moving component was eluted with alcohol and the eluates were evaporated to dryness.

Analysis and physical measurements: All the solids were analysed for their metal and nitrogen contents by standard methods. Conductance was measured by a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip-type cell with a cell constant of 0.65. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded in the range 250–4 000 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra (MgO) were measured with a VSU-2P spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities at varying temperatures (77–296 K) were measured by vibrational sample magnetometer-155.